

Noravank (Նորավանք)

also known as “Noravank Amaghu”

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Noravank is a medieval monastic and royal funerary complex located in the Vayots Dzor province of Armenia near the town of Yeghegnadzor above the Amaghu gorge. The site is comprised of several medieval ecclesiastical and smaller civil buildings. The walls surrounded the primary site were an 18th century addition. Noravank is still a functioning ecclesiastical site offering religious services to the local community, as well as a major tourist destination for the region. Today the site also houses a small museum complex, showcasing archaeological finds from the site and several interpretive panels. The most notable structures at Noravank are its two standing churches: Surb Karapet and Surb Astvatsatsin. Surb Karapet (Church of the Holy Precursor, Saint John the Baptist) was built in 1216-1227 as a commission by Prince Liparit Orbelian, after an earlier church with the same dedication was destroyed in an earthquake. The ruins of the original Surb Karapet can be found just south of the present church. The church features a domed cross-in-square floorplan. The cupola and roof have been destroyed and rebuilt multiple times due to regional seismic events. The addition of a large Gavit (narthex) was constructed in 1261, commissioned by Smbat Orbelian for whom the Gavit also serves as a burial vault. The Gavit features a number of elaborately carved khachkars, and the tympanum depicts the Virgin and Child seated on a rug adorned with floral, vegetal and geometric patterns - including stylized pomegranates, and the Holy Mother and Child are flanked by Isaiah and John the Baptist. Other scenes within the Gavit include a Crucifixion scene and the Ancient of Days. Adjoining the church is a rectangular side chapel with vaulted ceilings and circular apse dedicated to Saint Grigor (The Illuminator). The chapel was built by the architect Siranes in 1275, and also serves a funerary function - housing the resting places of a number of Orbelian family members. Surb Astvatsatsin (Church of the Holy Mother of God), completed construction in 1339 and served as the Syunik royal funerary church for Prince Burtegh Orbelian and several members of his family. The building itself was designed and sculpted by the Armenian Cilician architect and artist Momik, who died prior to the buildings completion in 1333 and he is entombed near the entrance of the church. It is among the most recognizable Armenian churches today for its unique two-story design and narrow cantilevered exterior double staircase along its west façade. The lower funerary vault features a rectangular plan, atop which sits a cross-in-square oratory with a colonnaded central dome. Relief carvings adorn both the church's façade and dome. The lower tympanum features the Virgin and Child enthroned, flanked by Gabriel and Michael and the upper tympanum features Christ flanked by Apostles Peter and Paul. An array of floral, vegetal, geometric, and figural reliefs adorns the buildings facades. Noteworthy are the images of crowned sirens and doves. The columns which support the conical dome depict the Virgin and Child alongside two donor portraits, one of whom holds a model of the church, representing the buildings Orbelian patronage.

Date Range: 1105 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Armenia

Region tags: Armenia

Vayotz Dzor, Armenia

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Pogossian, Z. "Princes, Queens, Bishops, Sultans: Seljuks in Syunik' and the Rise of the Monastery of Noravank.", *Orientalia Christiana Periodica* 89 (2023).
- Source 2: Van Lint, T.M., and Stone, M.E. "Two Unnoticed Armenian Inscriptiopns from Noravank", *:Revue des Études Arméniennes*, v. 26 (1997)
- Source 3: Luschi, C., L. Aiello, and M. Zerbini. "A Fidelity Made of Stone. The Armenian Architecture Seen from the Vayots-Dzor' Fringe." *Disegnarecon* 13, no. 25 (2020).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://sites.courtauld.ac.uk/crossingfrontiers/crossing-frontiers/armenia/noravank-monastery/>
- Source 1 Description: Maranci , Christina "Noravank." *Crossing Frontiers: Christians and Muslims and their Art in Eastern Anatolia and the Caucasus*

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Water source

Type of elevation

- Gorge

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
 - Leveling of ground
 - Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

- ↳ One single feature
 - Clearing

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - No

- ↳ A group of features:
 - No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– I don't know

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Worship and Memorial (Burial)

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: Associated with the Orbelian family

↳ Specify

–Other [specify]: Princes/Lords

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Metal

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: n/a

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

- ↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: kachkars
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Grave inscriptions
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Sirens, with crowned female heads and bird bodies

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: n/a

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: n/a

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: varied

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time
– I don't know

↳ Present part time
– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Presently serves as a public museum

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Noravank (Նորավանք), Maranci , Christina . “Noravank”. *Crossing Frontiers: Christians and Muslims and their Art in Eastern Anatolia and the Caucasus* , n.d..

<https://sites.courtauld.ac.uk/crossingfrontiers/crossing-frontiers/armenia/noravank-monastery/>.

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